

EdiCitNet News Template

Fields marked with * are mandatory.

EdiCitNet News

Dear all,

Please share the information related to your news using this template. We will use this information to produce news on the Website.

Don't forget to share at least one picture, to make the news more inviting.

News Information

* **News Title:** Please enter here a news title (Example: City Team Meeting in Berlin; EdiCitNet Workshop in Oslo, etc.)

Feel free to be creative !!!

Text of 30 to 150 characters will be accepted

ICRA presents the toolbox in the webinar "Innovation for SDGs: inspirational tools towards sustainability challenges."

* **Description:** Please enter here the text related to the news you are sharing. It can be a local event, meeting or other, related to Edible City Solutions (ECS) and/or EdiCitNet in your cities.

Text of 500 to 2500 characters will be accepted

The webinar series “Innovation for SDGs: inspirational tools towards sustainability challenges” focuses on opportunities and new trends in the fields of research and innovation. The goal was to debate and advance towards the achievement of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

In this sense Joana Castellar as a representative of WP2 lead (ICRA) delivered a presentation entitled “(Circular) nature-based Solutions”. The presentation delivered a critical discussion about what is and what is not a Nature-Based Solution (NBS), with special focus on the role of biodiversity for the conceptualization of NBS. Moreover, insights were given about the design of NBS for promoting circular management of resources in cities, especially water and food.

Finally, The EdiCitNet toolbox was presented, as an interactive space for knowledge sharing. Special attention was given to the diverse functionalities provided such as:

- An interactive Catalogue in which any person can create profiles for their (edible)NBS. Such profiles showcase technical information and offers a set of interactive functions that make it a true social network for users (civil society, urban planners, researchers).
- A Design and planning tool which enables users to create their own initiative(s) by giving insights about resources needed and food potential.
- A Performance assessment tool which enables user to compare the performance of these initiatives in terms of sustainability, urban challenges, and ecosystem services.”

Feature Image: Please send an image that will be displayed together with the news.

The maximum file size is 1 MB

Only files of the type png,jpg,jpeg,gif,bmp are allowed

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Additional Image (Optional): You can share here an additional image that will be displayed in the news.

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Hereby I confirm we have the rights to share this picture in EdiCitNet news.

URL: Here you can share an URL related to the news like a link to a video, website, etc.

https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=X4k5oFXI_CA

Date: Please confirm the date of the news you are sharing.

23/03/2021

Please specify a location related to the news you are sharing. (City, Address, Venue, etc.)

500 character(s) maximum

Contact Person

* **First and last Name:** Please enter your complete name. It will be displayed as author of the news.

Joana Castellar

* **Organisation:** Please enter the name of your organisation.

Catalan Institute for Water Research (ICRA) - Girona, Catalonia, Spain

* **Position:** Please indicate your position in your organisation.

Postdoctoral researcher

* **City & Country:** Please indicate the city and country where you are contacting us from.

Girona (Catalonia), Spain

* **Email:** Your email will not be shown in the news, unless you explicitly indicate it below. We will use it to contact you if we have any question.

jcastellar@icra.cat

I want my Email to be displayed in the news.

- Yes
 No

Social Media

* I agree to share my news on the EdiCitNet Twitter and/or Instagram

- Yes, both of them
- No, none of them
- Only on Twitter
- Only on Instagram

Additional Comments:

500 character(s) maximum

Contact

heimelen@hu-berlin.de